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A STUDY ON THE INTEGRATION OF LOCAL CULTURE INTO EFL TEACHING MATERIALS FOR JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Teaching material is becoming one of the important elements in teaching and learning process, especially for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) beginner learners. The teaching material presented may become harmful or useful to learner progress based on the appropriateness of the material to learners and the delivery. Indonesian Junior High Schools students are categorized as starter EFL learners, especially in the West Papua Province context, and at this age they are living close to their culture. In accordance with the 2013 Indonesian National Curriculum, which emphasizes the integration of local culture, this study aimed to examine the local culture integration in EFL teaching materials in the West Papua Junior High School environment. This study employed a qualitative paradigm using a purposive sampling technique and gathered information from 12 EFL Junior High Schools teachers across 6 different regions in West Papua Province. In-depth interviews were used to collect data on the perception of EFL teachers related to the teaching material used and the integration of local culture in EFL teaching material. The results showed that there was no West Papuan local culture included in accessible EFL teaching materials used so far. In fact, EFL teachers worked hard to simplify and modify the teaching materials available due to increasing student interest in learning English and the limitations of the resources they could access. This highlights the urgent need for additional EFL teaching materials with content adapted to the local culture of West Papua to support student learning.

KEYWORDS: Teaching Material, Local Culture, EFL.

1. INTRODUCTION

In language teaching, the teaching and learning materials (TLM) are also known as instructional materials that are becoming one of the important elements alongside teachers, learners, teaching methodology, assessment, and other contextually related factors. Good language instructional materials are aligned with other elements including teachers' language proficiency, cultural background of teachers and learners, learners' learning style, learners' interests, classroom conditions, availability of teaching sources, and other related aspects. As stated by Richards (2005), teachers, learners, and contextual variables all contribute to shaping effective language instructional materials. Therefore, materials in language teaching are becoming the central focus and source of information for learners to experience, learn, and apply the skills gained during the course of study. Teaching/learning language materials are not only textbooks but include anything which can be brought into the class to promote and facilitate the learning of a language. They can be linguistics, auditory, visual or kinesthetic aids that can be presented in print, as cassettes, live performances, on CD-ROMs, DVDs or, increasingly, over the internet (Tomlinson, 2001 in Nikoopour and Farsini, 2011).

In the context of teaching/learning at school, the official curriculum in vigor is also a major factor. In West Papua Province, Indonesia, the Curriculum 2013, referred to as K-13, is still used as the basis for instruction in most Junior High Schools, even though a newer curriculum has been developed at the national level, referred to as 'Kurikulum Merdeka' or 'Merdeka Belajar'. The Curriculum 2013 promotes the inclusion of culture in teaching/learning materials, as Indonesian Government Regulation No 32 concerning the National education Standard (SNP) mandates the inclusion of local culture and other local aspects in the curriculum framework. Bao (2016) and Mukundan et al (2016) in Oktarina, Inderawati, and Petrus (2022) affirm that students' inheritance is one of key points that needs to be taken into consideration in the development of teaching materials. Jiang (2000), Turkan and Celik (2007), and Phyak in Alakrash et al (2021) highlight the importance of integrating local culture into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching because learners are born within their own local culture, and this familiarity can be leveraged to facilitate their learning.

In West Papua Province EFL is generally taught in Junior High Schools at the starter or foundation level. Teaching EFL to students at this level will inevitably

face challenges related to many underlying factors related to the students' life outside school. Students at this age are mostly still living within their own culture because they are not old and mature enough to live separately from their parents. In this context, considerations that need to be taken into account include intellectual capacity, attention span, varieties of sensory input, surrounding factors, and the 'here and now' nature of communication (Brown, 2001). Therefore, inserting local culture in teaching EFL may help learners to feel comfortable in learning English. As explained by Renner (1994), teaching or learning a language will become much more meaningful for the learners when supported by familiar experiences, because these learners do not have yet had many experiences related to the English language. Furthermore, this approach is supported by the National Curriculum 2013 or K 13 which promotes culture in the process of EFL teaching/learning.

The Indonesian Central Government produced an English handbook for teachers to support the K 13 curriculum. This English handbook was distributed freely to schools in hard and soft copy versions through the Educational Department (Dinas Pendidikan). However, Indonesia is a diverse country with many cultures, so that the book provided cannot cover all cultures. In particular, this book does not really show local cultural content relevant for Papua. Some researchers have done studies on the Junior High School EFL textbooks used, namely 'When English Rings a Bell', and found that the books contain some Indonesian cultures, in particular: (1) Santosa (2015) claims that the 7th Grade textbook incorporates up to 73.63% of Indonesian cultures; (2) Erlina et al. (2018) found that the Indonesian culture content in textbook for the 8th Grade was 6.4% from paragraph analysis and 43% from picture analysis, while for the 9th Grade textbook it was 16.9% from paragraph analysis and 88.7% from picture analysis. Another frequently used textbook series entitled 'English in Focus' was analyzed by Silvia (2016). She found 40% Indonesian culture content in the 7th Grade's textbook, and 79% in the 8th Grade textbook. These studies reveal that, at some levels, the incorporation of Indonesian local culture is still limited or missing; furthermore, they did not cover the issue of the specific regional culture in Papua. Therefore, this study was conducted to explore the perceptions of English teachers with respect to the integration of cultural aspects local to Papua or West Papua into the EFL teaching materials in West Papua Province.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. West Papua Province

West Papua or Papua Barat Province is one of the five provinces in eastern Indonesia at the western end of Papua Island, bordering the country of Papua New Guinea which occupies the eastern end of the island. West Papua Province is located on the Bird's Head Peninsula at the western extremity of Papua Island. West Papua Province consists of 7 regencies, namely Manokwari, Manokwari Selatan (South

Manokwari), Pegunungan Arfak (Arfak Mountains), Teluk Wondama (Wondama Bay), Teluk Bintuni (Bintuni Bay), Fakfak, and Kaimana. Manokwari City is the provincial capital, and Manokwari is considerably more developed compared to the other six regencies. The topography varies between regencies; while Arfak Mountains Regency has mostly mountainous terrain, the other regencies are dominated by low-lying coastal plains as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Administrative map of West Papua Province, Indonesia.

Local culture from West Papua Province can be expressed through local languages, arts (song, dance, and crafts), local house designs and ways of living, traditions, beliefs, thought patterns, and customs.

2.2. Local Culture and Material Development

Local culture from West Papua Province can be expressed through local languages, arts (song, dance, and crafts), local house designs and ways of living, traditions, beliefs, thought patterns, and customs. This variety means that there are many issues that can be encompassed in instructional material development. In EFL teaching/learning, we often read and hear a lot of opinions given by many experts and researchers about the insertion or the integration

of local culture into language teaching. Issues related to language and culture appeared in the 1990s, an era when many aspects of life were seen as becoming more complex, in particular related to education and development (Kramsch & Hua, 2016; Kaharuddin et al., 2025; Rahman, 2017). In general, the concept of culture in a broad sense relates to what and how people think, believe, create, and appreciate things and processes. In a more restricted sense, a culture can mean a distinctive group of people with shared feelings, interests, historical backgrounds, and experiences (Brislin, 1981 cited in Margana, 2009); culture can also be expressed as a "way of people" (Lado, 1952 in Khan, 2016; Nursaadah et al., 2025).

In fact, language and culture cannot be separated,

they are intrinsically bound together because language is itself a part of culture. Teachers and students entering the English classroom are bringing in their culture along with themselves. Therefore, this phenomenon cannot be avoided and should not be neglected or ignored; as explained by Margana (2009), aspects of the learners' local culture need to be taken into account in the process of EFL teaching and learning. Related to this need, Kramsch & Hua (2016) explain four ways to conceptualize the connection between language and culture in ELT: (1) English as identified with Anglo-Saxon cultures attached to English-speaking nations; (2) English as a vehicle for multinational cultural aspects of modernity, development, and prosperity; (3) English as a common language (*lingua franca*) for global communication that enables contact with global culture, essential for entrepreneurial and cosmopolitan individuals; and (4) English as world language that formed the basis for Spanglish, Singlish, Chinglish, and other hybrid languages of diaspora, travel, worldliness, resistance or entertainment. The fourth point of Kramsh & Hua's concept is strongly related to what issue is being discussed. What is more, Tomalin (2009) claims that culture is the fifth language skill based on the reason that English is an international language and plays a key role in the ongoing process of globalization.

Indonesia is a complex and diverse country with many different cultures. The major islands and island groups such as Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Bali, Nusa Tenggara, Ambon, and Papua each have their own complex variations in local culture. Ucar (2016) cited in Romrome and Ena (2022) states that local culture is the main driving factor that forms the difference between one small group and another. Furthermore, Romrome and Ena explain that because local culture plays a key role in shaping and creating an individual's personality, characteristics, mindset, thought processes, behavior patterns, and habits, it is indisputable that local culture can influence the ways people learn (2022). In addition, Butarbutar et al (2019) assert that learning style can be governed by the local culture.

The advantage of using local culture in teaching EFL is to help learners to better understand the ideas presented, as every language has its own specific vocabulary with certain features where the meaning

is bound to the culture as well as to the literal meaning of each word (Khan, 2016). In line with that concept, Kramsch (1993) affirms that in learning a foreign language, the learners' culture and the foreign or target culture must be placed side by side to support the learners in understanding the foreign culture. Furthermore, Yassi (2017) advocates that inserting learners' local cultural context into EFL teaching and learning may provide benefits for learners; for example, EFL learners will be able to differentiate the harmful aspect of target language cultural contexts with respect to their own local culture when learning English, promoting local culture conservation. This process can have a positive impact on learners' integrity, producing not only smart learners but also promoting "noble character". What is more, Yassi claims that putting the learners' local culture and target culture together can build and strengthen learners' character and moral values, with benefits in terms of protecting themselves from losing their original character.

3. METHODOLOGY

This qualitative study aimed to evaluate EFL teachers' perceptions with respect to the integration of local culture in EFL teaching materials for Senior High Schools in West Papua Province, Indonesia. In terms of local culture, this study focused on the Papuan culture in West Papua Province.

The sampling approach of this study was purposive, actively seeking EFL teachers from different Senior High Schools across West Papua Province that confirmed their willingness to take part in the study and agreed to be interviewed as source participants. The research participants (respondents) comprised 12 EFL teachers from 12 different Junior High Schools representing 6 out of the 7 regions in West Papua Province. The details of the schools and teachers involved are shown in Tables 1 and 2. No EFL teachers from Manokwari Selatan Regency responded to the invitation to join this research, therefore there was no information from this regency. However, the data collected from 6 of the 7 regencies can give a general picture of conditions in West Papua Province related to the issue of integrating local culture into EFL teaching materials for Senior High Schools.

Table 1: Participating English Teacher School affiliations.

No	Regency	School	Village	School Code
1	Tel. Bintuni	SMP Perintis Stengkol 3	Vodamneem	Bintuni 1
2	Tel. Bintuni	SMP YPK	Tanah Merah	Bintuni 2
3	Manokwari	SMP N 6	Wosi	Mkw 1
4	Manokwari	SMP N 2	Pardani	Mkw 2

5	Manokwari	SMP N 10	Amban	Mkw 3
6	Manokwari	SMP N 3	Kwawi	Mkw 4
7	Fakfak	SMP N 1 Kokas	Sekar	FF 1
8	Tel. Wondama	SMP N 1 (1)	Wasior	Wondama 1
9	Tel. Wondama	SMP N 1 (2)	Wasior	Wondama 2
10	Tel. Wondama	SMP YPK Aitumieri	Maniwak	Wondama 3
11	Kaimana	SMP N 3	Krooy	Kaimana 1
12	Pegunungan Arfak	SMP YPPGI	Saugemeba	Pegaf 1

Table 2: Participating English Teacher Characteristics.

No	School Code	Teacher Code	Sex	Educational Background
1	Bintuni 1	T/Bin 1	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
2	Bintuni 2	T/Bin 2	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
3	Mkw 1	T/Mkw 1	M	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
4	Mkw 2	T/Mkw 2	M	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
5	Mkw 3	T/Mkw 3	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
6	Mkw 4	T/Mkw 4	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
7	FF 1	T/FF 1	M	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
8	Wondama 1	T/Won 1	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
9	Wondama 2	T/Won 2	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
10	Wondama 3	T/Won 3	M	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
11	Kaimana	T/Kai 1	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching
12	Pegunungan Arfak	T/Pegaf 1	F	Bachelor's degree in EFL teaching

The data in Table 2 show that all the EFL teachers had the same educational background, i.e., a Bachelor's Degree (S1 in Indonesian) in EFL Teaching. This leads to the assumption that they had attained similar levels of basic knowledge and skills with respect to core professional tasks such as skills in teaching English as a foreign language; understanding the National Curriculum and topics that should be taught; awareness of student needs; knowledge of English literature and English linguistics; and familiarity with known issues in dealing with EFL teaching and learning. This basis coupled with experience should have provided them with a strong understanding of English language and its cultural contexts which should help them in

teaching and promoting student learning.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Local Culture and Educational Material Development

The interviews were conducted via phone call after the interviewer and interviewee had agreed on the interview schedule. The conclusions drawn from the interviews with respondents representing their information about materials, materials related to local culture, materials development, and problems were tabulated. Responses related to EFL teaching materials are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Teacher perceptions on EFL Teaching Materials.

No	Teacher Code	Teacher Response on EFL Teaching Materials
1	T/Bin 1	Even though the school has a handbook for teachers, I have my own materials too. I also usually get the materials from the internet.
2	T/Bin 2	We have got the materials from the Educational Department, but I usually look for the materials from the internet too.
3	T/Mkw 1	I got the book from the school.
4	T/Mkw 2	I use a book from Intan Pariwara and material from the internet.
5	T/Mkw 3	I have got the book from the Educational Department, but I find additional material from the internet.
6	T/Mkw 4	I have my own materials; I got them from the internet.
7	T/FF 1	I got the materials from the local Education Department (Dinas Pendidikan) and I have also obtained some myself.
8	T/Won 1	I develop my own materials based on the recommended book, I mostly look for materials from the internet.
9	T/Won 2	I mostly look for materials from the internet.
10	T/Won 3	I got my own materials and looked them up on the internet.
11	T/Kai 1	I have got the book from the Educational Department, but I find material from the internet.
12	T/Pegaf 1	I have got old books from the Education Department, and my school just bought a new book for me to use. If the internet is available, sometimes I try to see material from the internet too.

The responses in Table 3 show that the sources or books that EFL teachers have and use are varied. Some teachers got the teachers’ handbook prepared or provided by their schools or the Education Department, but most teachers obtained and used their own teaching materials. For their own teaching materials, they mostly used different books or got them from the internet if they had internet access.

They said that these materials tend to be easier to understand and many of these non-government materials available were fairly simple for the students too. They can choose from the material available online based on the level of difficulty and suitability for the students. Their perceptions regarding the inclusion of local (Papuan) culture are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Teacher responses regarding Materials related to Local Culture in EFL Materials.

No	Teacher Code	Is Local Content Included?		Does Papuan culture need to be included? If so, why?		Do materials available need modification?	
		YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO
1	T/Bin 1		√	To help my students in EFL learning		√	
2	T/Bin 2		√	Contextual materials help my students.		√	
3	T/Mkw 1		√	Contextual materials help students.		√	
4	T/Mkw 2		√	To help students in EFL learning.		√	
5	T/Mkw 3		√	To help students in EFL learning, to know local culture.		√	
6	T/Mkw 4		√	To help my students in EFL learning, to know local culture.		√	
7	T/FF 1		√	To conserve/protect Papua culture, contextual materials help students.		√	
8	T/Won 1		√	To help students in EFL learning, to know local culture and protect.		√	
9	T/Won 2		√	To help students in EFL learning, to know local culture.		√	
10	T/Won 3		√	To help my students in EFL learning.		√	
11	T/Kai 1		√	To help students in EFL learning, to know local culture.		√	
12	T/Pegaf 1		√	Local content helps my students in EFL learning.		√	

The data in Table 4 demonstrate that none of the teaching and learning materials available contained local culture from West Papua or Papua more generally. Therefore, the teachers needed to work extra on making modifications themselves, whether in order to simplify the materials or to develop supporting material based on the local context, especially useful vocabulary that relates to the learners’ environment and daily lives. All teachers agreed on the importance of the insertion of local culture into EFL teaching materials. They believed that it could help and support their students in learning English as a foreign language. Besides, they

also agreed that, by inserting local cultural context, students will be better able to understand and communicate West Papuan culture and conserve the local culture. This is especially important for the indigenous West Papuan students. The problems faced by EFL teachers from the six different regencies are summarized in Table 5. Note that in this context internet data limitations refer to the (often prepaid) data quotas (in Indonesia internet access is typically purchased in time-limited GB quotas) and/or bandwidth. Explanatory notes are given in square brackets.

Table 5: Problems faced by EFL teachers in West Papua.

No	Teacher Code	Problems
1	T/Bin 1	Limited access to the internet because of limited data [quota], unstable internet, limited books at school, sometimes blackouts [power cuts], limited self-development, I don’t have a good printer.
2	T/Bin 2	Not enough sources, access to internet data [quota] is a bit expensive for me, not enough self-development, limited office tools and supplies (computer, printer, ink, paper).

3	T/Mkw 1	Limited English sources at school, unstable internet, I have to buy my own internet data [quota], limited self-development, I don't have my own printer and at school the printer was not working.
4	T/Mkw 2	Limited English sources at school, unstable internet, I buy the internet data [quota], limited self-development.
5	T/Mkw 3	Limited English sources at school, unstable internet, I cannot to always buy the internet data [quota], sometimes blackout [power-cuts], limited self-development, insufficient office tools and supplies.
6	T/Mkw 4	Limited English sources at school, unstable internet, I buy my internet data [quota], sometimes blackout [power-cuts], limited self-development, I don't have good printer.
7	T/FF 1	Limited access of internet because of limited data [quota], unstable internet, limited books at school, sometimes blackout [power-cuts], limited self-development, limited office tools and supplies (computer, printer, ink, paper).
8	T/Won 1	Not enough sources for EFL teaching sources, I have to buy the internet data [quota], and the internet is unstable, blackout sometimes [power-cuts], limited self-development, limited office tools.
9	T/Won 2	Sources are limited, a bit expensive to always buy internet data [quota], blackout sometimes [power-cuts], limited self-development, limited office tools.
10	T/Won 3	Limited English sources at school, unstable internet, I buy the internet data [quota], limited self-development, limited office tools.
11	T/Kai 1	Not enough sources for EFL teaching sources, I have to buy the internet data [quota], and the internet is unstable, blackout sometimes [power-cuts], limited self-development, insufficient office tools and supplies to support us.
12	T/Pegaf 1	Even though I have old and new books, still I have to get more from the internet so that I need to buy more internet data [quota] for it, limited self-development, limited office tools.

Based on the information gathered from the teachers as displayed in Table 5, the most common and arguably the biggest problem was the lack of resources at each school. The second biggest problem was the limitations of internet access as a way for teachers to look for English teaching materials, due to the cost of buying internet quota themselves and the low quality of the internet services available (low bandwidth and interruptions). The lack of office support, and opportunities for self-development as practitioners were also common problems.

5. DISCUSSION

The discussion focuses on four main issues raised by the results of the study.

5.1. *Issues related to the educational background of the teachers*

All EFL teachers have the same educational background, as stated in Table 2 above. This issue is important because by having the same educational background, it can be said that all EFL teachers who become the informants of this study have a similar level of understanding on EFL teaching and learning issues such as curriculum, syllabus, teaching methodology, classroom management, material development, students learning style, teaching media, and so on. Thus, overall, they know what to do with their English classes.

With their understanding of knowledge, teaching

theories, curriculum, teaching materials available, students' needs, strength and weakness, situation or environment, and all the conditions in their places, they are assumed to be able to reduce the gap between all the aspects mentioned. As can be seen in Table 4, all teachers have made some modifications to their teaching materials. In fact, teachers are aware that the teaching materials provided or available were not suitable for their students. Therefore, they have to modify the teaching materials in order to achieve the teaching and learning goals and meet students' needs. According to Thompson (1992) cited in Darwish (2012), in teaching and learning situations teachers interrelate with the environment and situations; some experience conflict between their beliefs and practices and some do not; some live with unsolved conflicts but some may try to resolve the conflicts.

The background knowledge of EFL teachers is crucial, as the way they teach can impact students' ability to comprehend English skills. Prior knowledge of EFL teachers can create a more engaging and meaningful learning experience, making concepts easier to understand and remember, and fostering affective language learning. As Nunan (2005) in Darwish (2012) remarks, teachers in the class have several tasks to perform besides teaching; these typically include observing student interactions, developing materials for each day, discussing relevant topics, brainstorming for the

selected topic(s), problem solving, creating games or activities that can stimulate and assist students' understanding, etc. In addition, what teachers do in the classroom is a reflection of what they know and believe, the knowledge and thought processes which deliver the underlying framework of classroom actions (Richards & Lockhart, 2007). Therefore, the

background knowledge of teachers is important.

5.2. Issues related to teaching materials

All teachers had their EFL teaching materials, even though there were variations between individuals. In the words of some of the teachers:

T/Bin2	<i>We have got the book as our teaching materials from Regional Educational Department, but I usually look for materials related from the internet because there are many examples of English teaching materials there.</i>
T/Mkw 4	<i>I have got my own teaching materials, but I also look for relation available materials on the internet.</i>
T/Won 3	<i>I have my own materials because I bought them from the store. Besides, I also look for additional materials.</i>

From the explanations above it can be concluded that, although teachers already got official teachers' handbooks as their basic teaching materials, they tend to adapt their teaching materials. Adaptation or modification in language teaching is a common strategy for teachers in order to support their students in learning. This strategy is accommodated because teachers are aware that they have a variety of students in their class; their students may have different English proficiency levels, and the students may come from different backgrounds. As claimed by Brooks (1999), Harper & Jong (2004), and Tarman & Chigisheva (2017) cited in Raza (2018), teachers have to remember the diversity of their students in the classroom when explaining the materials they use.

Teaching EFL is not as simple as people think. Teachers meet and see different students with different levels and backgrounds daily, even more so if they teach in different classes or grades, especially those who are teaching in the rural areas. The availability of teaching and learning sources such as textbooks can help by providing a learning guide that allows students and teachers to see what can be done during the educational process (Tomlinson, 1998). As stated by Cunningsworth (1995) in Ayu (2020), teaching materials are seen as the main instrument

for shaping the knowledge, behavior, and discipline of students, increasing students' knowledge and experience, as resource to achieve teaching and learning goals and objectives, even though the materials may only be partially successful because they may be less attractive and poorly aligned with students' interests. What is more, according to Richards (2019) teaching materials are categorized as key component in language teaching and learning because they provide a basis for teaching and learning activities which are carried out in the classroom that enable learners to familiarize themselves with linguistics, as well as social and cultural aspects. In other words, materials made available as teaching and learning guides should be pitched at the level of the learners, use approaches familiar to learners, develop learners' ability, designed to reach aims and objectives, be attractive and able to motivate, and support students' learning.

5.3. Issues related to local culture

All teachers agreed that West Papua or Papua local culture needs to be included in EFL teaching and learning materials because it can attract and help students in learning English. This is exemplified in the following quotes from individual teachers.

T/Mkw 3	<i>I agree that local culture inserted into English teaching because it motivates students to learn. Students are triggered to study English so that they can talk about them in English. Besides, for Papuan students, they can conserve their culture, and for non-Papuan students, they can understand well of local culture. Consequently, I make modification to my materials by using simple sentences and using vocabularies surroundings.</i>
T/Won 1	<i>Yes, I think using local culture in teaching EFL is a good idea, because I have tried several times to use local stories, I made a very short story for reading, my students were enthusiast and active in the class. They also spoke actively although they mix the language Indonesian and English. Some of them just reply in very short and simple phrases too. We do not really have magazines, textbooks, or story books here, so I mostly look for materials from the internet to get ideas.</i>
T/Kai 1	<i>Yes, I agree to mix the local culture into EFL teaching materials because I believe students will be motivated and triggered in studying. Also, they will know more about local culture. For this, I modify my teaching materials to simplify or adapt with local vocabulary.</i>

Even though all teachers already had their teaching materials, they modified their materials by simplifying the existing teaching materials and/or preparing their own teaching materials which could include local content. Several types of simplification were made; for example, the use of vocabulary that

relates to local content in their teaching materials and using simple sentences. Teachers want their students to feel comfortable and confident in learning English. Sometimes, the materials were not covering the stages laid out in the National Curriculum, but students were learning English in the classroom. This

situation was considered better than strictly following the National Curriculum, but students often cannot catch up with all the materials or topics discussed. Hanifa et al. (2024) explained that materials adaptation establishes fundamental elements for language classes where teachers can expand the resources to achieve teaching outcomes. This is done mainly to create communicative and more effective learning related to the unique characteristics of students. Teachers adopted such approaches in order to support their students and enable them to readily understand the materials they needed to learn. Adaptation is often necessary because the ready-made materials available may not match with the situations and the students encountered by the teachers (Cunningsworth, 1984 cited in Marand, 2011; Byrnes, 2004 & Don, 2020 in Ahamat & Kabilan, 2022).

So far, what EFL teachers in this study have done to simplify materials was mostly related to the vocabulary used. This is because they are aware that vocabulary is indeed related to the four core skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). When learners' master the basic vocabulary needed, they will be able to work on and improve those four skills. As stated by Richards and Renandya (2002) cited in Rahma, Tahir, and Talib (2023), the ability of a learner in learning a language can be measured through vocabulary, and through vocabulary it can be seen how well a person is capable of speaking, listening, reading, and writing. With vocabulary, a person can convey ideas through oral and written media. Therefore, developing vocabulary related to topics that learners are familiar with can help learners to easily acquire and remember the new words. In further steps, learners will be encouraged to become confident in using this vocabulary. This is what is called support to enhance student learning.

All EFL teachers also agreed that using local culture in teaching EFL can support Papuan students' awareness and understanding of their own culture, while non-Papuan students could gain information and improve their understanding of local culture at the same time as they are learning a foreign language. As asserted by Rahman, Ali, & Badriah (2022), Oktarina, Inderawati, Petrus (2022), and Aminullah, Sada, & Sudarsono (2019), using local culture in EFL teaching materials can provide additional benefits to students such as positive psychological effects with respect to their emotions and enthusiasm for learning, retaining the attention of students, reducing students' burdens, enabling students to communicate about themselves in English, as well as supporting students in improving

their English skills.

In addition, inserting local culture or local wisdom into EFL teaching and learning materials can become a manifestation of and assist in maintaining local culture or local wisdom itself. Learning a language includes understanding the culture, attitudes and norms behind it, at the same time as learning the language itself.

5.4. Issues related to teaching problems

All the EFL teachers shared similar problems which can be categorized as limitations or lack of learning facilities and media namely; (1) the limited resources available in their schools; (2) limited internet access because they have to buy their own internet data quotas which means they have to pay extra from their own pockets to be able to search for their teaching materials; (3) the internet services are still unstable in this region; (4) the electric power-cuts (blackouts) affect the internet access, not only when they occur in the home or place of work, but also when they cut power to the transmission towers which relay the internet signals to the surrounding area; (5) limited access to opportunities for self-development or shortages of ongoing training as EFL teachers; and (6) limited access to office tools and supplies to support the teaching and learning process, including the production of handouts.

Issues number 1 – 4 mentioned are related to internet access and the instability of the internet network, even the blackout issues add to the limitations on internet access to find sources of teaching materials and appropriate media. The internet offers a wide range of resources and opportunities for EFL teachers and their students. Teachers can access many sources such as different kinds of dictionaries, digital libraries, games, quizzes, online news, articles, videos, podcasts, and many more. As discussed by Supriadi, Patak, and Korompot (2023), with limited internet access teachers face problems in getting references and materials resources that can be used to promote learning. They also face problems in sharing these with their students in digital or on-line forms.

Issue number 5 is related to self-development. The EFL teachers agreed that they have challenges in accessing self-development opportunities, especially those who are living outside of Manokwari Region. Even though they already had a bachelor's degree in EFL Teaching, they still felt the need for ongoing training and development to gain more skills and knowledge, especially in terms of developing their teaching skills and adapting to modern media and methods.

This is evidenced in the following quotes:

T/Won 2	<i>There are almost never any activities for English teachers in this region. Actually, we do need it, we need to develop ourselves, especially in materials development, teaching skills, using modern tools, and more.</i>
T/Pegaf 1	<i>I never attended the English teacher's activity. It is because my school's location is rather far from the city of this region. I have to stay in the city for a few days if I want to follow such activity. The activity was from the Provincial Educational Department so that the activity was for teachers in general. There was none for English teachers.</i>

This situation was similar in most regions and was perceived as a problem, because it was holding back the development of EFL teachers' ability to develop their ideas, teaching skills, self-confidence, self-development, knowledge, current issues, and maybe more. Activities specifically designed for EFL teachers, such as workshops, round-table discussions, or regular meetings with other EFL teachers, could help encompass various aspects that need addressing. These include refining teaching methods, keeping up with current educational trends, developing language teaching expertise, improving self-management skills which leading to the improvement of students' learning outcomes and professional growth. This sort of approach is called the improvement of education and self-quality (Priajana, 2017).

The final issue that arose was the limitations in terms of office tools and supplies to support the teaching and learning process. Why are they considered important? The availability of office tools and supplies can effectively support EFL teachers in many ways, so much so that in many conditions they become essential. These tools and supplies may involve both traditional and the more modern digital tools now often considered essential, from articles such as textbooks, workbooks, whiteboards, markers, and writing materials, to computers and/or laptops and projectors, etc. The accessibility of appropriate and sufficient teaching and learning facilities will support teachers and students in the teaching and learning process (Dalyono, 2001 in Hardiana et al, 2023). On the other hand, a lack of

adequate school facilities can have a negative impact on both teachers and students, as insufficient school facilities can directly affect the teaching and learning process (Olugbenga, 2019). Therefore, making school facilities accessible and available is important as a foundation for the processes of teaching and learning.

6. CONCLUSION

This study shows that EFL teachers agree with the integration of local culture into teaching materials. Teachers believe that it has a positive impact in supporting students in learning English. This study also shows how teachers adapt and modify their teaching materials to suit their students by using local content, because the official materials available do not contain West Papuan cultural content. In addition, EFL teachers are experiencing challenges in terms of insufficient or lacking sources of material, internet access, self-development opportunities, and access to basic equipment to support them in teaching.

Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop EFL books or other teaching materials adapted to West Papua with local Papuan culture content as supplementary material to support EFL teaching and learning in this province. Furthermore, there is a need for self and professional development activities for EFL teachers, and to improve school facilities to support the improvement of teaching and learning processes, including internet access and office equipment.

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